

Project¹ Number: 745936

Project Acronym: PlasmaSolution

Project title: Demonstration and implementation of an integrated process for the plasma-enhanced chemical solution deposition of PMMA-multicomponent coatings on wood and wood-based substrates

Periodic Technical Report

Part B

Period covered by the report: from 01/07/2018 to 31/08/2020

Periodic report: FINAL

¹ The term ‘project’ used in this template equates to an ‘action’ in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

Note: This report was published together with the archived project administration, excluding documents containing private and personal data. The dataset is available openly at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4161291>

1 Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and Overview of the progress

This project set out to implement a novel process for the plasma deposition of protective coatings on wood and wood-based substrates that includes the three steps:

- (a) Plasma pre-treatment for optimized substrate wetting and liquid uptake,
- (b) Application of PMMA-based liquid formulations including various additives,
- (c) Film formation via fast plasma curing.

The implementation followed several objectives, which are explained in details in the following sections, presenting the work carried out per work package in comparison to the original plan.

A Data Management Plan has been drafted at the start of the action², completed within the first 6 months, and published openly³. During the action, the plan was further updated and moved to the European ARGOS platform, as soon as it got available. On the platform, the updated DMP is openly available.⁴ Another update iteration is foreseen to be published following the project, which will be linked to the previously published plans. More details on the updates and relations are provided in section 3 of this report.

The milestones of the project were:

- M1 Construction of plasma modules finished and parts ordered.* The project has fully and timely achieved this milestone.
- M2 Device completed and functional.* The project has fully and timely achieved this milestone. However, the work had to be revisited and repeated under new premises arising from results of a later work package.
- M3 Pre-treatment operation points optimized for coating and impregnation mode.* The project has fully achieved this milestone, but included a slight delay due to mitigation measures in WP 1.
- M4 Liquid formulation and corresponding plasma parameters optimized.* The project has failed to achieve this milestone.
- M5 Generalized description of PECSD process deducted.* The project has failed to achieve this milestone.

The results and their exploitation, as well as the reasons for deviations from the work plan and the performed mitigation measures are explained in detail in the following sections.

² <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/plans/18705/export.pdf>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3530162>

⁴ <https://argos.openaire.eu/explore-plans/publicOverview/1314b654-4e93-46b3-bc97-7d075ab5376e>

1.1 Objectives

The project has achieved some of its objectives and milestones. However, corrective action will be required.

The overall scientific goal of demonstrating and implementing an integrated process of plasma pre-treatment, application of a liquid formulation, and film formation by plasma curing was divided into three main **scientific objectives**:

Objective I: Building the integrated device. This objective has been fully met.

Objective II: Optimization of the deposition parameters. This objective was partially met.

Objective III: Demonstrating the technique's capability and priming the industrial implementation. The project has failed to meet this objective.

The project has fully achieved the **training objectives**. The planned training activities and outcomes planned in the proposal were highly exceeded.

The work carried out during the reporting period towards the achievement of the listed objectives are described in measurable details in the sections below.

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per WP

1.2.1 Work Package 0 – Management

The management activities were pursued actively throughout the project duration. The financial and administrative part of the project was covered by the faculty's administrative unit, whereas the researcher took on the responsibility to oversee the action's budget. The researcher responsibly led all further management aspects of the fellowship, initiating and conducting all activities towards Consortium Agreement, Data Management Plan, Career Development Plan, progress and supervision meetings, Training activities, Purchases, Communication and Dissemination, as well as all project documentation. Project activities were discussed with the supervisor on a daily basis during morning coffee meetings, with a more detailed update on project activities on a weekly basis. Status meetings and status updates including the co-supervisor from the partner institute were initially held in two-weekly intervals, but intervals were later prolonged to better reflect the project activities. Moreover, formal meetings with both supervisors and representatives from the company foreseen as secondment host were held once per year, as defined in the three parties' consortium agreement.

The project proposal presented work with three collaborating parties, besides the host this included the nearby Jožef Stefan Institute as continuous collaboration partner and the Italian company Certottica S.c.r.L. as host for the secondment and network partner for the dissemination and exploitation of project results. In order to enable a fruitful collaboration, a **Consortium Agreement** was drafted and signed based on the DESCA model agreement in the version 1.2.4 from October 2017.

The **data management plan** was drafted with support from different units at the host university (see sect. 1.2.8.2), published online, and regularly updated, as described in detail in section 3.

The training activities were planned and implemented with the help of a **Career Development Plan** (CDP) and the Vitae Researcher Development Framework⁵. Based on a canvas approach (see Figure 1) derived from the business model canvas⁶, a first draft of the CDP was developed shortly after submission of the project proposal in September 2017. The completed CDP for the first year was finished in May 2018, on time before the start of the action. Updated CDP versions were discussed and confirmed with the supervisors in February 2019 and February 2020.

Figure 1 Initial canvas approach to prepare a Career Development Plan

The **transfer of knowledge from researcher to host** was conducted on different levels:

- Several pieces of equipment were developed for a multitude of applications to allow for all applications the department may want to deal with in the future, as they are foreseeable from the department's core research fields.
- Technical staff members at several chairs of the hosting department were trained to operate and maintain the equipment; selected staff members were introduced in sufficient depth to continue the development of the equipment and the field.
- The personal network was shared among the colleagues at the host, to allow for a meaningful continuation of the research activities in the field of non-thermal plasma applications.
- Additional network connections with local partner organizations were created and collaborative activities were implemented during the project period.

These successful activities were honoured by the host such, that a Plasma Center⁷ was established, which shall continue the activities in the future. For the present time, the researcher was elected into the function as head of the Plasma Center.

The **transfer of knowledge** from host to researcher took place mainly through hands-on training during the research activities (see subsections 1.2.2 through 1.2.6 and 1.2.8.1), counselling and advice, as well as establishing professional connections to extent the network and provide collaboration opportunities.

The researcher was very well integrated in the department on several levels. In the research group, coffee meetings every morning and close collaboration on an everyday basis ensured a

⁵ <https://www.vitae.ac.uk/researchers-professional-development>

⁶ OSTERWALDER, Alexander; PIGNEUR, Yves. Business model canvas. Self published. Last, 2010.

⁷ <http://www.bf.uni-lj.si/en/wood-technology/department/organisation/plasma-center/>

good integration. On a formal level, the researcher was integrated through the habilitation, election as assistant professor, inclusion in the department's senate, and the mentoring of a doctoral student, all from before the official start of the project. During the project period, collaborations with every chair and every single research group at the department took place. Moreover, collaborations with seven other faculties at the host university were started by the researcher. External collaborations took place with several national and international partners, including academia, public institutions, and companies. These collaborations were included in the submitted proposals coordinated by the researcher (c.f. sections 2.7.2, 2.7.3, and 2.7.4) and in the implemented PKP project (c.f. section 2.5.9). Results were partially published (c.f. sections 2.1, 2.2, and 2.3) or are still in preparation for publication.

1.2.2 Work Package 1 – Build-up of demonstrator

The build-up of the plasma device was initiated well before the start of the project. In order to ensure a timely and successful development, the project was set out to use proven materials for dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) plasmas, such as ceramic half-finished products and brass work pieces for the electrodes. Further, the electronic components necessary for the required high-voltage generator were acquired from the start-up company Plasma Green GmbH, that the researcher was a part of founding before the start of this project. Moreover, the researcher was included in the academic system at the host through the habilitation as assistant professor and as supervisor of a doctoral thesis, both of which were confirmed half a year before project start. The doctoral work included setting up a plasma device with a novel operational mechanism, which was intended for co-use as well within this project.

Figure 2: Plasma device implemented with the doctoral student at the host (left) and view into the device during plasma operation (right).

The activities and measures before project start led to a first plasma device being available at the host from the start of the project (see Figure 2). Unfortunately, several problems arose within the first few months, which had to be mitigated: Firstly, a defect appeared in the electronics obtained by the start-up company. This defect was concerning the microcontroller operation and was not possible to fix on site. Unfortunately, the focus of the start-up and the co-workers at the company had changed since the initial agreement, and the support from the German colleagues by the time of the defect was insufficient. Therefore, the development of an high voltage power supply was started, for which the intellectual property and competences shall remain at the host. Secondly, the transfer of the plasma reaction from the preliminary setup on metal substrates to wooden substrates proved more complicated than expected. In particular, the focus was on an implementation possible to scale up to industrial purposes, for which the initial approach proved insufficient. Instead of a direct DBD with included gas feed, which was

planned to be similar to the equipment the researcher had set up at the previous employer, a screening of constructive variations was conducted to identify the suitable design. Moreover, continuing discussions with the industrial contacts and partners indicated that different techniques should be considered for the application of the liquid formulation. Therefore, the concept of an integrated device encompassing two plasma discharges and the liquid application was dropped. Instead, the design was changed to keep the plasma devices modular enough to be able and operate them at the various machines for liquid application present at the host and within the industrial network. The two lines of remediation activities are described in detail in the following subsections.

Figure 3: First power supply, partially including parts from the start-up company.

1.2.2.1 Power supply design

After the problems arising with the power supply the project had got provided, the designing a new power supply was carried out under strong constraints. On one hand, the budget had not accounted larger amounts for the power supply, so the new design had to be set up in the most economic way possible. On the other hand, the design had to be simple and straight-forward enough for the host department to be able to maintain and troubleshoot the equipment after the researcher finishes the stay at the institution. Further, the development had to be conducted fast enough to timely continue with the project. Moreover, the IP of the previous design had to be respected, as it lies with the start-up company, and has thus to be left out entirely.

The conditions for these mitigation measures were only possible to meet by strongly reducing the complexity of the system and by relying on the most simple and well-known approaches, that were possible to work out within the described frame. In order to meet these conditions, the following four general approaches were taken:

Figure 4: Cockcroft-Walton generator prototype. Early and professional PCBs (left) and assembled setup (right).

1. High voltage potentials are commonly produced through Cockcroft-Walton generators, which are relatively simple stacks of diodes and capacitors. Due to their simple and cost-efficient design, the researcher implemented a prototype generator of this kind, as shown in Figure 4. However, these provide direct current HV, which would require additional switching for DBD plasma applications. Moreover, using mains power at 50 Hz causes far too long charging times for the entire stack, rendering it unsuited for plasma applications. The power supply is instead kept for demonstration purposes in lectures, such as the ionized nature of flames. The design has been openly made available online through the projects repository deposits.

Figure 5: Small-scale HV power supplies based on fluorescent tube drivers and Flyback transformers. Assembled devices (left) and view into the internal electrics (right).

2. Hobbyist showcase many cases of simple high voltage generators on the internet, where a HV Flyback transformer is driven through an electronic choke for fluorescent light tubes. These circuits are very cheap and simple to set up, and they provide sufficiently high voltages to ignite arcs and other plasmas. However, the overall output power of these components are too low to be able and operate plasma devices of sufficient sizes to perform meaningful treatments. The prototype setups implemented by the researcher displayed in Figure 5, however, are perfectly suited to demonstrate different kinds of plasmas and discharges, and to highlight the corresponding properties. These small HV power supplies have been since used many times in the lectures hold by the researcher, they were reproduced by other academic groups for similar education purposes, and the design is made available openly through online repositories. A scientific article describing the setup and the utilization for education purposes has not yet been

finished, but shall enable high voltage demonstration in many more institutions of education at different levels worldwide.

Figure 6: Zero voltage switching HV power supply with small oscilloscope, front view (left) and internal wiring (right).

3. Zero-voltage switching circuit designs are published on the internet for up to 500 W, and assembled circuit boards from these very designs can be commercially obtained at low cost. Such design is among the most energy-efficient designs, as it is operating double-resonant with the attached HV transformer. The researcher put these circuits together with cost-efficient low-voltage power supply components for secure operation. Further, a small oscilloscope unit was included for diagnostic purposes, as displayed in Figure 6. These power supplies were most suitable for gliding arc plasma jets, however, the resonant operation proved troublesome and did not yield a stable operation of DBD plasmas. They were thus used at the host for further localized plasma treatments with simple plasma jets, but did not comply for the project's main objectives. The design of the power supplies has been published openly through the repository deposits of the project, and a scientific article describing the power supply and the related plasma jet tools is in preparation at the time of submission of this report.

Figure 7: Flyback HV power supply with simple Flyback driver board (left) and as entire assembly (right).

4. The design of a fixed-frequency Flyback power supply required the design of a simple and cost-efficient, but durable driver circuit. After durability issues with driver ICs in circuits out of the manual, a simplified combination of a bulk junction transistor switching a power MOSFET was designed, tested, and integrated into a complete assembly as displayed in Figure 7. The designs are published openly through the repository deposits of the project, and a

scientific article describing the power supply and a related surface barrier discharge plasma is in preparation at the time of submission of this report.

Figure 8: Updated Flyback driver with fixture for HV transformer on the PCB

The communication activities of the four approaches and their worthwhile utilization are still on-going, but also the development of the design is continuing within the Plasma Center. Colleagues from the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, and are conducted openly and collaboratively through GitHub.⁸ These developments include the usage of ATX power supplies for a more hobbyist-friendly implementation, as well as for improved driver designs, and they include a Flyback driver that includes a possibility for current measurements and a fixture of the HV transformer on the printed circuit board in standardized Eurocard dimensions (see Figure 8).

1.2.2.2 Plasma tool design

The preliminary investigations prior to the project had utilized a direct DBD plasma in a closed reaction chamber. For this project, a transfer to an open plasma with possibility for cover gas introduction was planned. In order to make the DBD technology better scalable to industrial processes, a novel approach was tested, which exploits the conductivity and high dielectric permittivity of wood, to use the substrates like an electrode at floating potential. This idea was included in the doctoral works of Jure Žigon, whose PhD thesis is mentored by the researcher.

Figure 9: Construction details of FE-DBD device (left) and COMSOL simulation of electric fields (right).⁹

⁸ <https://github.com/SebastianDahle/Plasma-PSU>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.21268/20190318-13>

The operational principle of the floating electrode (FE) DBD ranges between a gliding discharge known from metal treatments and single-electrode medical DBD devices, that utilize the skin as counter-electrode. The wood substrate passing below the electrode forwards the electric field through its conductivity and its dielectric permittivity, thus inducing plasma ignition only between electrode and substrate, but not in-between the electrodes power with opposite polarity high voltages (c.f. Figure 9). These works are shared between the doctoral thesis (mechanical construction, plasma experiments) and this project's work (electrical simulations, advice on construction and operation details, plasma characterization). With the available high voltage power supplies, however, the plasma setup did not reach total independence of substrate thickness and would only work in a stable manner on relatively thin strips of wood. Although this approach proved not suited for the further works in this project, the setup is interesting for a variety of applications and is further used at the department including in the doctoral thesis.

Figure 10: Direct DBD device with CNC-controlled moving table.

In order to accommodate larger samples allowing for samples up to $30 \times 50 \text{ cm}^2$, as well, a regular direct DBD was implemented on a large moving table, which is controlled via a CNC system (Figure 10). The device is thus suited for a variety of laboratory and semi-industrial samples as well as for preparation of sample sizes relating to hot presses and mechanical testing equipment at the department. Unfortunately, the intensity of the direct discharge and the absence of an enclosure limiting the vapour pressure of volatile substances, this device led to such strong evaporation even for those compounds with highest vapour pressures foreseen for work package 4, that no film formation was observed. To remediate this setback, a surface barrier discharge plasma device was thus implemented. In addition to that, the lessons learnt from direct DBD and FE-DBD devices led to a new plasma tool concept, which eliminates the need for mechanical positioning systems, as described below.

Figure 11: Self-adapting DBD system "PlasmaSwing" mounted to a conveyor device (left), with activated plasma discharge in close-up view (middle), and in demonstrator device including the conveyor belt (right).

DBD plasmas are the most efficient non-thermal plasma techniques for a huge variety of applications. A critical parameter for this, however, is the precise control and the repeatability of the discharge gap, as this defines discharge parameters and thus effects the outcomes of the treatments. Typically, the control and repeatability are achieved through elaborate positioning systems with precise control of at least one axis perpendicular to the work piece's surface. This accounts for a substantial part of the plasma devices cost and complexity, and demands additional safety mechanisms for an industrial implementation. Moreover, this becomes especially problematic for work pieces with changing dimensions or an unsteady feed mechanism. Based on the experiences with other DBD devices, the researcher formulated a novel concept, using a double- or multiple-lever system that mechanically maintain the correct work distances without the need of an external control system. This idea was titled "PlasmaSwing", it was implemented for testing in a simple prototype (see Figure 11) and a patent application was filed. To enhance the dissemination and exploitation activities supported by the hosts technology transfer office, a second, down-sizes prototype was implemented for further testing and live demonstration purposes. In favour of the planned project activities, however, further testing activities were not followed at high intensities, yet.

Figure 12: Surface barrier discharge as simple device (left), improved setup over a conveyor belt (middle), and in a down-sized, integrated version (right).

After the lack of success for curing with a direct DBD, a surface barrier discharge was implemented, which is a less intense type of setup with larger plasma treatment area at comparable power consumption. Using a printed circuit board as electrode, a parallel position system was developed that fitted to the majority of devices in the host lab (Figure 12, left). During a Bachelor thesis that used the surface discharge for pretreatments of wooden substrates before application of outdoor coatings (see section 1.2.9), the design of the surface discharge was improved to better meet the small working distances at required precision, while also including an oil reservoir to restrain the discharge and buffer the device temperature (Figure 12, middle). In addition to that an integrated device was implemented to encompass smaller electrodes, which had been initially used for testing the design before ordering the larger electrodes. Thus, these test electrodes became a useful tool for small laboratory treatments and further preliminary experimentation, e.g. on the treatment of viscose fabric (Figure 12, right).

During the development of the high voltage power supplies (c.f. 1.2.2.1), simple setups were employed for testing the electronics and the ability to ignite and stably maintain electrical discharges. These included a Jacob's ladder travelling arc and derived small-scale barrier discharge setups. Later on, these setups were further housed and integrated with a pressurized air supply for cooling purposes, thus leading into simple plasma jet tools.

Figure 13: DBD plasma jet with polymer housing (top) and with wooden carrier plate in operation (bottom).

A simple DBD plasma jet was set up using a glass Pasteur pipette as disposable dielectric barrier hold by a PG16 cable gland. The setup was fixed to a cast epoxy polymer block as holder, to which insulated housing and the pressurized air connector were fixed as shown in Figure 13. This setup proved ideal for testing purposes as well as for plasma treatments in liquids, whereas it is not overly well suited for most surface treatments, as the long, narrow pipette tip leads to the decline of the plasma discharge beyond the afterglow, with mainly just ozone remaining as reactive component in the gas stream.

Figure 14: Gliding arc plasma jet on a CNC positioning system with integrated Raspberry Pi control unit.

The initially used traveling arc setups were later contained within another cast epoxy polymer block with pressurized air connector, thus yielding a gliding arc plasma jet. This jet proved well suited for various localized plasma treatments of surfaces, that was applied by several colleagues in early experiments including on 3D printed parts, microwave-dried wood and others. In order to allow for meaningful treatments, one such plasma jet was included on a CNC positioning system (Figure 14), thus making it possible for students and staff to use plasma treatments with minimal training or supervision required. Moreover, this integrated system is well equipped for many hobbyist and do-it-yourself applications, as well as for research labs on a tight budget, and the design currently gets disseminated for these purposes, thus linking into the Open Laboratory Equipment branch of the Open Science movement.

Figure 15: Gliding arc jet in mobile digestorium for PECVD applications.

In order to allow for the gliding arc jets to be operated with reactive gases as well as utilize them for plasma polymerization and plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition, one setup was integrated into a small digestorium chamber with appropriate ventilation system Figure 15. Thus, a plasma deposition system was made available for safe use in the laboratory environment. The setup was utilized for early experiments with superhydrophobic and superhydrophilic coatings together with the ERC project CABUM.

Figure 16: Hand-held gliding arc jet device from SKOZ project.

Moreover, the gliding arc design was used in a collaborative project with the secondary school Gimnazija Vič (see section 2.5.11), where three selected pupils constructed and set up a hand-held plasma prototype as shown in Figure 16.

1.2.2.3 Summarized results related to WP 1

The main technological achievements of this work package are the diverse set of plasma equipment, which can be utilized as tools for a variety of applications. The innovative aspect about these tools is the simple construction and cost-efficient implementation, which allow for a wide re-use across research laboratories, small companies, hobbyists, and other entities with limited budgets that are looking into using plasma technology. These outcomes are published

openly and collaboratively through several platforms or repositories, whereas the correlated scientific publications are partially still in preparation. However, instead of a single paper, this work package includes no less than three scientific publications.

Moreover, one entirely novel approach was taken and a patent application was filed for this innovative new technological solution. Moreover, the results were disseminated through various events and platforms with the support of the hosts technology transfer office.

1.2.3 Work Package 2 – Wetting and liquid-uptake adjustment

The adjustment of plasma pre-treatments for optimized wetting or liquid uptake with different liquid formulations were found to be more complex on more levels than expected. Although the complexity of the interaction between liquids and heterogeneous materials such as wood were known, the results yielded effects beyond the surface energies of substrates and liquids, which proved too complex to be combined into a generalized model description during the action. Individual effects were reported in scientific publications, though, including differences in penetration, compositions of different coatings formulations, and others.

Moreover, previously unknown effects were observed, indicating influences by plasma surface treatment deeper inside the work pieces than previously reported. Changes in moisture content, conductivity, and dielectric parameters as well as with an apparent impact on the modulus of elasticity, which were found to occur at least 10 – 100 μm deep inside the material. In addition to that, these changes of substrates' properties have an influence on the plasma parameters during the ongoing surface treatments. Although not apparent in chemical composition through infrared spectroscopy, these effects have strong implications on how to implement processes for functionalization of wood surfaces by plasma treatments, while also rendering possible additional potentials for applications, e.g. in microwave drying of wooden work pieces.

In summary, the initially envisioned output of this work package was not yielded. Instead, unexpected observations did pave the way for future projects and further potential applications, which might lead to an entirely new line of research within the scientific field.

1.2.4 Work Package 3 – Plasma diagnostics

Plasma diagnostics were carried out together with colleagues from the Jožef Stefan Institute, using Optical Emission Spectroscopy and an ultra-high speed CMOS camera. Further, electrical diagnostics were performed together with a colleague who graduated from the Faculty for Electrical Engineering prior to becoming staff member at the host department. The plasma diagnostics did not provide innovative insights by themselves, but were an essential part in the interpretation of results from WP 1, WP 2 and WP 4, and were therefore included in a large part of the publications.

In deviation from the initial work plan, no Langmuir probes were used for diagnostics due to technical limitations. Instead, Fastcam and electrical diagnostics provided insights into the plasma processes.

1.2.5 Work Package 4 – Coatings without additives and fillers

The preliminary results on plasma curing of liquid precursors were carried out in a closed reactor setup.¹⁰ After first difficulties with the electronics were sufficiently solved, further problems were encountered with the transfer from a closed setup towards an open direct DBD setup. For the envisioned applications, however, discussions with the mentor as well as with potential industrial users revealed that a closed batch reactor did not come into account. Therefore, the plasma tool design was revisited as described in section 1.2.2.2. Although the experiences led to a new, innovative technical solution for conventional plasma treatments, no working solution was found. Many variations and precursors were tested, but none was able to induce significant curing; instead, the plasma led to such enhanced desorption or evaporation even for the larger molecules, that plasma-induced reactions were not successful. Moreover, the UV emissions from open plasma discharges are too weak in intensity to work competitively against curing by UV lamps, even when operating the plasma in inert cover gas streams, as oxygen diffusion into the gas streams in open systems are still too high, thus quenching the intensity. Due to the delay caused by technical problems in WP 1 and the available laboratory time significantly cut short by the COVID pandemic in the second project year, no working solution to the problems was found until the end of the project.

The initial planning had foreseen two papers from work packages 4 and 5, covering the plasma deposition processes. However, due to the encountered difficulties, the researcher was not able to produce these publications.

1.2.6 Work Package 5 – Complex coatings

The fifth working package was not possible to conduct in a meaningful way due to the delays in work package 1 and especially due to the difficulties and problems encountered in work package 4. Individual activities out of WP 5, which were connected with national projects and existing topics, were preponed to include them in the ongoing work. In particular, these were interactions of the plasma discharge with so-called liquefied wood¹¹ that might provide an alternative way of curing this bio-based formulation or might help improve the properties of the final product. Unfortunately, the same difficulties were encountered as with work package 4, thus preventing any reusable outcome of these works.

1.2.7 Secondment

A secondment was planned at the industrial partner, Certottica S.c.r.l., with the beginning on March 1st, 2020. Unfortunately, the company is located at Longarone in northern Italy, within the cluster of the COVID pandemic that spread in the area in February 2020. Therefore, the secondment was impossible to conduct during the action.

The main goals of the secondment were training outcomes for the researcher with experience on working in an industrial environment, as well as for the promotion of the project outcomes. The same goals were included in collaborations with companies located closer to the host in Slovenia and through collaboration with the hosts Knowledge Transfer Office.

¹⁰

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320519220_Plasmaunterstutzte_chemische_Flussigphasenabscheidung_-_Neue_Perspektiven_fur_Polymerbeschichtungen

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.40865>

1.2.8 Training activities

The training activities performed for research, transferrable and personal competences in line with the Career Development Plan (see 1.2.1) are described in detail in the following sections. In addition to these, teaching skills were improved through mentoring several students' theses (see 1.2.9) as well as through participation in several lectures for the hosts and for partners' study programs (see 1.2.10).

1.2.8.1 Research skills

In the course of the project, experimental skills were obtained through hands-on training as documented through the publication list. These skills include the handling of wood-based substrates, characterization of coatings' properties including adhesion strength, surface free energy, colour, gloss, outdoor weathering, artificially accelerated weathering, and liquid uptake. Moreover, dielectric characterization, residual moisture content determination, and plasma diagnostics by optical emission spectroscopy and electrical measurements were trained and conducted.

In deviation from the initial plan, two techniques were omitted from the experimental and training activities. On one hand, the progression of the work packages did not indicate a meaningful inclusion of fungal decay measurements. Further, the equipment developed during the action was not suited for utilization of the Langmuir probe technique; instead, electrical measurements for diagnostic purposes were conducted.

1.2.8.2 Transferrable and personal skills

A large degree of the transferrable skills were obtained through online courses, as these were the most compatible way and provided the least interference with the project work. Areas of online training included Project planning and monitoring competences, e.g. through the Scrum, PMBOK and Prince2 systems, Leadership competences, e.g. through Feedback, Leadership and Coaching specializations, as well as Innovation and Entrepreneurship competences, e.g. through Design Thinking, Social Impact and Open Innovation specializations. Rhetoric skills were obtained through workshops with a special focus on outreach towards non-specialists. Training and support regarding Open Science in general, particularly on Open Research Data and Data Management Plans, was obtained through colleagues at the hosts Social Science Data Archives unit and the corresponding spokespeople at the hosts central University Library, as well as through participation in the Open Science MOOC.¹² Moreover, grant-writing workshops were attended, both general workshops about Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe proposals, as well as a focused workshop programme by the host for ERC applicants. Finally, Slovene language courses were taken over the entire duration of the project, to obtain language skills required for interactions with colleagues and with national partner organizations.

1.2.8.3 List of training courses and workshops attendance

During the project period, the following courses and workshops were attended in line with the training objectives:

30. **Mentoring of doctoral students – Active encouragement for successful preparation.** University of Maribor. 2020.

¹² <https://opensciencemooc.eu/>

29. **Addressing innovation potential in Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe.** University of Ljubljana & Europa Media Trainings. 2020.
28. **Smart Leadership.** 3h. ABC Accelerator d.o.o. 2020.
27. **Design Thinking.** 3h. ABC Accelerator d.o.o. 2020.
26. **Webinar "How to stay sane in academia? Ways for combating stress and uncertainty."** 1.5h. The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers. 2020.
24. **Open Science Workshop.** 6h. University of Ljubljana. 2020.
23. **Research data management workshop.** 6h. University of Primorska, Koper. 2020.
22. **ERC grant writing training programme.** University of Ljubljana. 2019.
21. **COST ACTION FP1407 WG4 Workshop.** 7h. InnoRenew CoE. 2019.
20. **Slovene language courses.** 320 WU¹³ in total. University of Ljubljana.
 - *Slovene language course (for university employees).* 80 WU. 2020.
 - *Slovene language course (for university employees).* 60 WU. 2020.
 - *Slovene language course (for university employees).* 72 WU. 2019.
 - *Slovene language course (afternoon course).* 80 WU. 2019.
19. **Public Engagement and Popular Science Writing.** 8 WU. University of Ljubljana. 2018.
18. **Whiteboard SEO.** Udemy. 2018.
17. **SEO Training.** Udemy. 2018.
16. **Social Media Monitoring.** Udemy. 2018.
15. **Scrum Awareness.** Management Plaza. 2018.
14. **Free Social Media Analytics.** Quintly. 2018.
13. **PRINCE2.** 8 weeks. Management Plaza. 2018.
12. **PMBOK Awareness.** 6 weeks. Management Plaza. 2018.
11. **Coaching Skills for Managers.** Selected modules (2/4). Coursera, University of California, Davis. 2018.
 - *Setting Expectations & Assessing Performance Issues.* 4 weeks. 2018
 - *Managing as a Coach.* 4 weeks. 2018.
10. **Inspiring Young People In STEM.** FutureLearn, National STEM Learning Centre, UK. 2018.
 - *Using Feedback to Improve.* 2 weeks. 2018.
 - *Activities and Improving Communication.* 2 weeks. 2018

¹³ WU = Work unit, equals 45 min

- *Planning Activities*. 2 weeks. 2018
 - *Resources and Diversity*. 2 weeks. 2018.
9. **Model Thinking**. 12 weeks. 3-4h each. Coursera, University of Michigan. 2018.
 8. **Organizational Leadership Specialization**. Selected modules (3/6). Coursera, Northwestern University. 2018.
 - (5) *Leadership Through Design Innovation*. 4 weeks, 3-4h each. 2018.
 - (2) *Leadership Communication for Maximum Impact: Storytelling*. 4 weeks, 3-4h each. 2018.
 - (1) *High Performance Collaboration: Leadership, Teamwork, and Negotiation*. 3 weeks, 3-4h each. 2018.
 7. **Innovation & Entrepreneurship - From Design Thinking to Funding**. 6 weeks. Coursera, EIT Digital & UC Berkeley. 2018.
 6. **Innovation & Entrepreneurship - From Basics to Open Innovation**. 6 weeks. Coursera, EIT Digital & UC Berkeley. 2018.
 5. **Leadership in 21st Century Organizations**. 10 weeks. Coursera, Copenhagen Business School. 2018.
 4. **Social Impact Strategy: Tools for Entrepreneurs and Innovators**. 4 weeks, 2-4h each. Coursera, University of Pennsylvania.
 3. **Design Thinking for Innovation**. 5 weeks, 1-2h each. Coursera, University of Virginia. 2018
 2. **Career Brand Management**. Coursera, State University of New York. 2018.
 - *Strategic Self-Marketing and Personal Branding*. 4 weeks, 2-4h each.
 - *Career Brand Development and Self-Coaching*. 5 weeks, 3-5h each.
 - *Strategic Career Self-Management*. 6 weeks, 3-5h each.
 1. **Giving Helpful Feedback**. 5 weeks, 1h each. Coursera, University of Colorado, Boulder. 2018.

1.2.9 Supervision of Bachelor, Master and PhD students

The following theses were formally mentored or co-mentored, several are still on-going works. In addition, the researcher participated informally with the supervision of other M.Sc. and doctoral students.

6. Dona Strmčik: **The impact of plasma processing on the wear of tooth gears**. B.Sc. thesis (as co-mentor, at FTPO in Slonvej Gradec). On-going (started April 2020).
5. Megi Pilko: **Influence of plasma treatments on the performance of surface systems during outdoor exposure**. B.Sc. thesis. Graduated 18.09.2020.
4. Domen Kmetič: **Treatment of surfaces with plasma to improve the quality of bonding**. B.Sc. thesis (as co-mentor). On-going (started January 2019).
3. Dejan Todorovič: **Influence of FE-DBD plasma treatment on the wettability of wood**. B.Sc. thesis. Graduated 13.09.2019.

2. Bahram Mahdavi-pour: **Analysis of air cleaning with dielectric barrier discharges**. Doctoral thesis. On-going (started April 2018)
1. Jure Žigon: **Surface treatment of wood with floating electrode dielectric barrier discharge plasma**. Doctoral thesis. On-going (started March 2018).

1.2.10 Teaching activities

The researcher finished his habilitation at the host before the start of the project. Including a lecture or practical course as elective topic in the study program, however, would have required a 5-year accreditation, and was thus not possible. Instead, a joint course was implemented with colleagues (see section 2.5.10). Further, individual lecture hours in existing study courses of colleagues were taught by the researcher. In addition to that, the researcher was closely included in supervision activities with students (see section 1.2.9).

9. **Plasma Treatment of Wood**. University of Ljubljana. 18.12.2019. Double lectures in course “Modern Processes of Surface Treatments of Wood”.
8. **Utilization of non-thermal plasmas for improved wood bonding**. University of Ljubljana. 5.12.2019. Double lecture in course “Technology of Wood Bonding”.
7. Evening event: **Teaching in the lab**. Clausthal University of Tehcnology. 6.11.2019.
6. Summer school: **Interphases of Biobased Materials**. Clausthal University of Technology & University of Ljubljana. September 2019, 4 SWS & 3 SWS, respectively. Double lecture and supervision of laboratory work.
5. **Plasma Treatment of Wood**. University of Ljubljana. 07.01.2019 & 11.01.2019. Two double lectures in course “Modern Processes of Surface Treatments of Wood”.
4. **Utilization of non-thermal plasmas as pretreatment and means for curing of wood coatings**. InnoRenew Center of Excellence & University of Primorska, Koper. 06.12.2018. Colloquium.
3. **Utilization of non-thermal plasmas for improved wood bonding**. University of Ljubljana. 29.11.2018. Double lecture in course “Technology of Wood Bonding”.
2. Summer school: **Interphases of Biobased Materials**. Clausthal University of Technology & University of Ljubljana. September 2018, 4 SWS & 3 SWS, respectively. Double lecture and supervision of laboratory work.
1. **Aufreinigung von Ammoniak-Gas aus Tierställen mittels Plasmatechnologie – Von der Forschung zur Ausgründung**. *Purification of ammonia emissions from livestock breeding facilities using plasma technology - from academic research to a spin-off company*. Life Science Day, BioRegion & HAWK Göttingen. 06.09.2018. Presentation in workshop.

1.3 Impact

The project has fully achieved the impact lined out for the project period in section 2.1 of the description of the action. With the career goal to be appointed as professor related to plasma-modification and surface engineering, the acquired methodological skills related to coating applications, industry collaboration, wood sector, plasma diagnostics, and industrial research and development are as relevant as they were in the planning stage of the project. The practical

experiences with teaching and public outreach provide a base as public sector employee and a responsible university lecturer. The soft and transferrable skills, as well as the intercultural experiences, open mind-set, and problem-solving skills are core competences to the envisioned position.

1.3.1 Impact on the researcher's career

The project strongly enhanced the potential and the future career prospects of the researcher.

The habilitation as assistant professor for Wood Science and Technology provided the researcher the chance to take up responsibility for supervision and mentoring of students, but also to participate in the administrative processes of the university as a senate member at the department. Both opportunities were well utilized to extend the researcher's experience and track record, including the mentorship of 1 PhD and 2 B.Sc. theses, and the co-mentorship of another 1 PhD and 2 B.Sc. works.

The researcher was able to strongly extend the scientific and professional network through the project, as represented by the diverse co-authorships included with the scientific publications, by the huge increase of the online network including on social media channels, but also by the consortia members in submitted project proposals.

During the project period, the researcher coordinated a proposal for an ERA Chair that included 50 partner organizations and a large part of the host university. The coordination of this proposal brought about an invaluable experience for the researcher, and extended his professional network greatly. Although the project was not granted, this coordination among other project activities enhanced the researcher's recognition in the respective academic communities, and let to his inclusion in further project proposals, such as one recently submitted for a call within Horizon 2020's Bio-based industries joint undertaking (c.f. section 2.7.4).

The publication activity of the researcher grew through the project. The average publication rate increased from 3 publications per year before the project to 3.3 publications per year after the project, averaging over the entire academic career, so far. Before the project, the highest publication rates amounted to 5 and 6 publications per year in 2014 and 2015, respectively, whereas rates had been lower since then due to the researcher's heavy involvement in teaching activities and in a technology transfer project founding a start-up company. During the project, the publication activity increased again, amounting to 5 publications per year in 2019, while for 2020 and 2021, so far, 2 journal articles are published, 6 are under review, and 10 further are in preparation close to submission. Thus, the summarized publications for 2020 and 2021 will be at least 50% higher than the maximum rate from before the project.

Similarly, the activity concerning conference contributions increased from an average of 3.6 contributions per year before the project to 4.3 conference contributions per year after the project, as averaged over the entire academic career, so far. The highest rate before the project amounted to 7 conference contributions in 2016, whereas during the project both in 2019 and 2020, 10 conference contributions were presented, each year, equaling to twice the average rate and representing an increase of 43% above the maximum rate from before the project.

In addition to the publication activities, the researcher conducted 30 reviews of scientific publications during the project period, which are documented through the Publons record. Furthermore, the researcher was involved three times in evaluating proposals for Horizon 2020 projects since the start of the project.

The researcher entered organizations concerned with and included in policy-making for academia and research on national and European levels, thereby being enabled to engage with shortcomings of the current system and policies. The researcher is strongly convinced, that this will yield improvements for the next generation of scientists, and will thereby prove worthwhile to have invested the efforts.

Since the MSCA project was granted, the researcher submitted 10 applications for junior and associate professorship positions. One application yielded an invitation to present before the committee, but none of the applications was successful.

The researcher's next career steps are primed through a preparatory project at University of Ljubljana before the submission of a proposal to the European Research Council for a Consolidator Grant. Meanwhile, the researcher will finish the habilitation process for the field of material physics at Clausthal University of Technology, in order to be better suited for positions as described in the career goals. Further, the researcher will continue to submit applications for professorship positions.

1.3.2 Societal benefits

The project's scientific results did not provide direct contributions to European policies or strategies. They do provide inputs towards resource efficiency and climate-friendly technologies, as well as to a sustainable bioeconomy. Moreover, the outcomes enable wider stakeholder groups to explore and utilize these technologies, and to engage citizen to advance this field of science.

The new knowledge and equipment led to an enhanced innovation capacity at the host, as represented by the Plasma Center that was established on the basis of the project's results. Through the collaboration with companies throughout the region and in particular through an additional project that was acquired (see section 2.5.9), the industrial and societal needs were evaluated at a regional level. This did already provide new market opportunities for the collaborating companies, and is expected to induce a strengthened competitiveness and growth by paving the way for the uptake of plasma technology in these new market segments.

1.3.3 Relevant innovation activities

Innovation activities were addressed through the laboratory equipment developed and through demonstration devices built to implement a novel processing technique (c.f. sections 1.2.2.1 and 2.4). However, the innovative developments have yet to be validated in the industrial environment and introduced to the market.

1.3.4 European policy objectives

During the project period, the researcher engaged with the Young Academy of Slovenia, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, and the Research Data Alliance. In actively participating with these organizations, the researcher fostered recent European policies, including the vision for Europe towards Open innovation, open science, open to the world. A further priority of the researcher's collaboration with these organizations focused on the education of doctoral candidates and the continuation of the Bologna process, as well as the situation of early career researchers and the corresponding political framework.

1.3.5 Potential users of results

Aside from the scientific results advancing the corresponding fields in academia, four specific kinds of results are worthwhile for different potential users as described below.

A novel implementation of DBD plasmas was developed and a patent application was submitted covering the invention. This implementation is interesting for industrial applications of plasma discharges particularly for work pieces of changing sizes and geometries. Several activities were conducted under the advice and support of the host's technology transfer office to contact potential users, including events such as Start:IP in Vienna and written communications, for example through a technology offer on Enterprise Europe Network. Contacts with interested parties has been established, but did not yet lead to an industrial impact.

The various pieces of plasma equipment that was developed and implemented during the project are interesting for research labs and organizations with limited budgets as well as for hobbyists. They are thus being published as Open Lab Equipment and through collaborative platforms such as GitHub. The uptake is still limited, but selected pieces of the equipment have been reproduced, already, by research groups in Europe, e.g. at Masaryk University in Brno for educational purposes. This exemplifies that the insights and working materials are of potential interest for institutions of education, including universities or secondary schools. It is planned to provide Open Educational Resources for such purposes, but these materials have not been published until the submission of this report.

In general, plasma applications have yet to be taken up in the sector of wood-based industries. In order to foster the exploitation of the technology and better understand the barriers that have prevented a significant take-up, so far, a separately funded student project was acquired and conducted (see section 2.5.9). Follow-up activities are currently being planned together with a company distributing industrial plasma equipment and the potential users that stated interest in a continued collaboration during the students' project.

2 Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results

2.1 Conferences attended

In the proposal, four conference contributions were foreseen, targeting the 21st ICWSE, 18th PSE, IWC2019/2020, and IRG-WP 2020. While the first two had passed due to a delayed beginning of the project, the third one was exchanged for better suiting alternatives. The last planned conference was attended, but took place online due to the COVID pandemic.

In total, 21 conference contributions were published during the project period:

21. S. Dahle, J. Žigon, M. Petrič. **PlasmaSolution – Curing of coating formulations using non-thermal plasmas**. 51st IRG-WP, online conference, 2020
20. S. Dahle, J. Žigon, I. Uranjek, M. Petrič. **Performance of a water-borne stain on beech, spruce, MDF and OSB improved by plasma pre-treatment**. 51st IRG-WP, online conference, 2020
19. J. Žigon, S. Dahle. **Wood-Metal Bonding Strength Improved Via Atmospheric Plasma Pre-Treatment**. 63rd SWST international convention, Portorož, Slovenia / online, 2020

18. S. Dahle, I. Uranjek, J. Žigon, S. Medved. **Influence of Atmospheric Air Plasma Pre-Treatment of Veneers on the Mechanical Properties and Stability of Beech Plywood.** 63rd SWST international convention, Portorož, Slovenia / online, 2020
17. B. Mahdavi-pour, S. Dahle, J. Oberrath. **Plasma chemistry simulation of a planar dielectric barrier discharge in air.** International Conference on Plasma Science, Marina Bay Sands, Singapore, 2020
16. G. Lavrič, J. Žigon, S. Dahle, I. Karlovits, U. Kavčič. **Optical and abrasion properties of plasma treated and UV LED printed wood samples.** InnoRenew CoE International Conference, Koper, Slovenia, 2020
15. V. Udachin, S. Nagorny, S. Dahle, J. Adams, A. Schmidt, W. Maus-Friedrichs. **Characterization of photochromic diarylethene films produced via spin-coating.** Frühjahrstagung der Deutschen Physikalischen Gesellschaft, Dresden, Germany, 2020
14. S. Dahle. **Data Management Plan, FAIR and open research data.** Open Science Workshop, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 2020
13. J. Žigon, S. Dahle, M. Petrič, Matjaž Pavlič. **Enhanced abrasion resistance of coated particleboard treated with atmospheric plasma.** 30th International Conference on Wood Science and Technology, Zagreb, Croatia, 2019
12. S. Dahle. **Demonstrating experience in developing a research data management plan: needs for services, tools and policies.** Open Research Data in Slovenia, Maribor, Slovenia, 2019
11. J. Žigon, S. Dahle. **Improvement Of Plasma Treatment Efficiency Of Wood And Coating Process By Sodium Chloride Aqueous Solutions.** International Conference on Wood Science and Engineering, Brasov, Romania, 2019
10. S. Dahle. **Plasma-based deposition of solid films from liquid precursors.** 26th International Scientific Meeting on Vacuum Science and Technique, Njivice, Croatia, 2019
9. B. Mahdavi-pour, J. Oberrath, S. Dahle. **Impact of gas flow on dielectric barrier discharge for air purification.** 24th International Symposium on Plasma Chemistry, Naples, Italy; 2019
8. S. Dahle. **Desulphurization of biogas and of diesel exhaust gases using dielectric barrier discharges.** 8th Central European Symposium on Plasma Chemistry, Gozd Martuljek, Slovenia, 2019
7. J. Žigon, S. Dahle, M. Petrič. **Uporaba plazme za boljšo kompatibilnost površine lesa s premazi.** Prvi doktorski dan Bi(o)znanosti, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 2019
6. A. L. Arendt, S. Dahle, W. Maus-Friedrichs. **Deoxidation of copper surfaces by a dielectric barrier discharge plasma.** Frühjahrstagung der Deutschen Physikalischen Gesellschaft, Regensburg, Germany, 2019
5. B. Mahdavi-pour, S. Dahle, J. Oberrath. **The Influence of Electrical Properties of Wood on Dielectric Barrier Discharge plasma treatments at atmospheric conditions.** Frühjahrstagung der Deutschen Physikalischen Gesellschaft, München, Germany, 2019

4. J. Žigon, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **The influence of artificial ageing and treatment with FE-DBD plasma in atmospheric conditions on wettability of wood surfaces**. 3. Niedersächsisches Symposium Materialtechnik, Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Germany, 2019
3. B. Mahdavi-pour, S. Dahle, J. Oberrath. **Study of Single Filament Dielectric Barrier Discharge in Argon**. 71st Annual Gaseous Electronics Conference, Portland, OR, USA, 2018
2. J. Žigon, S. Dahle. **Zasnova naprave za obdelavo površin lesa z DBD plazmo s plavajočo elektrodo**. Srečanje Gozd in Les (engl.: Forest and Wood Summit), Ljubljana, Slovenia, 2018
1. J. Žigon, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **Wettability of wood surfaces with waterborne acrylic lacquer stains adjusted by DBD plasma in air at atmospheric pressure**. 11th International Symposium on Contact Angle, Wettability and Adhesion, New Jersey, USA, 2018

In addition to the published and presented conference contributions, the following conferences and workshops were attended:

11. **Workshop “Getting Ready for Horizon Europe”**, September 24th & 25th, 2020, online
10. **Eurodoc Conference and Annual General Meeting**, July 22nd – 25th, 2020, online
9. **Conference: “Research data and European Open Science Cloud”**, June 18th, 2020, online.
8. **Workshop “Research Data Management”**, January 9th, 2020, InnoRenew CoE, Koper, Slovenia
7. **Adriatic Wood Days**, December 2nd & 3rd, 2019, Dubrovnik, Croatia
6. **First UN Open Science Conference**, November 19th, 2019, UN Dag Hammarskjöld Library & Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition (SPARC), online.
5. **GZS Innovation Day**, September 25th, 2019, Brdo, Slovenia
4. **MCAA General Assembly and Annual Conference**, February 23rd – 25th, 2019, TU Vienna, Austria
3. **InnoRenew CoE / COST FP1407 workshop**, February 4th, 2019, Koper, Slovenia
2. **Final conference of COST action FP1407**, December 11th – 14th, 2018, Faculty of Forestry, Belgrade, Serbia
1. Conference **“Women in the digital future: Breaking stereotypes”**, December 7th, 2018, TU Munich, Germany

2.2 Scientific publications

In the proposal, four scientific publications were foreseen in correlation to the work packages. Based on the results and outcomes, four articles have been published by the end of the project period, and another nine manuscripts are either submitted or in preparation close to submission.

Scientific publications available under Open Access are:

4. J. Žigon, D. Todorović, M. Pavlič, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **The influence of selected parameters of treatment of wood with atmospheric plasma on the treatment process and wood wettability.** *Revija les*, 2020, 69(1), 71-84. <https://doi.org/10.26614/les-wood.2020.v69n01a05>
3. J. Žigon, J. Kovač, R. Zaplotnik, J. Saražin, M. Šernek, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **Enhancement of adhesives strength of wood-metal joints using atmospheric plasma treatment.** *Cellulose*, 2020, 27, 6411-6424. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-020-03212-8>
2. J. Žigon, S. Dahle. **Improvement of plasma treatment efficiency of wood and coating process by sodium chloride aqueous solution.** *PRO LIGNO*, 2019, 15(4), 260-267. ISSN 2069-7430
1. J. Žigon, S. Dahle, M. Petrič, Matjaž Pavlič. **Enhanced abrasion resistance of coated particleboard treated with atmospheric plasma.** *Drvena Industrija (Wood Industry)*, 2019, 70, 129-137. <https://doi.org/10.5552/drvind.2020.1960>

Additional manuscripts under review or in preparation at the time of submission of this report:

9. S. Ganguly, J. Žigon, K. Srinivasa, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **Combined plasma surface treatments and microwave drying of green wood specimens.** *MDPI materials*, in preparation
8. S. Dahle, J. Žigon, B. Gospodarič, M. Merhar, M. Petrič. **Open-source device for direct cold atmospheric plasma treatment of substrates.** *MDPI materials*, in preparation
7. S. Dahle, J. Žigon, B. Gospodarič, R. Zaplotnik, M. Merhar, M. Petrič. **Open-source integrated plasma treatment and CNC machining system.** *PLOSone*, in preparation
6. S. Dahle, M. Pilko, J. Žigon, R. Zaplotnik, M. Petrič, M. Pavlič. **An open-source barrier discharge plasma pretreatment reduces cracking of outdoor wood coatings.** *Surfaces and Interfaces*, in preparation
5. T. Gimpel, J. Žigon, C. F. Otto, D. Kržišnik, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **Wood surface nanostructuring and etching using a fs-pulsed laser.** *Holzforschung*, under review
4. S. Dahle, J. Žigon, M. Petrič, M. Kariž. **Plasma treatment of spruce wood changes bulk dielectric permittivity.** *Revija les*, under review
3. J. Žigon, M. Pavlič, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **Influence of artificial weathering on coated MDF pre-treated with atmospheric plasma.** *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, under review
2. J. Žigon, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **Dielectric and surface properties of wood modified with NaCl aqueous solutions and treated with FE-DD atmospheric plasma.** *European Journal of Wood and Wood Products*, under review
1. J. Žigon, M. Pavlič, P. Kibleur, J. Van den Bulcke, M. Petrič, J. Van Acker, S. Dahle. **Treatment of wood with atmospheric plasma discharge: Study of the treatment**

process, dynamic wettability and interactions with a waterborne coating.
Holzforschung, under review

Furthermore, a number of additional publications were published, which are in connection with or were enabled by this action, although not being a direct outcome of the project:

5. J. Žigon, J. Saražin, M. Šernek, J. Kovač, S. Dahle. **The effect of ageing on bonding performance of plasma treated beech wood with ureaformaldehyde adhesive.** Cellulose, under review
4. J. Žigon, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **Wettability of Wood Surfaces with Waterborne Acrylic Lacquer Stains Modulated by DBD Plasma Treatment in Air at Atmospheric Pressure.** Advances in Contact Angle, Wettability and Adhesion, 2019, 4, 41-56. Edited by K.L. Mittal. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119593294.ch3>, ISBN: 9781119592549
3. J. Žigon, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **Artificially aged spruce and beech wood surfaces reactivated using FE-DBD atmospheric plasma.** Holzforschung, 2019, 73(12), 1069–1081. <https://doi.org/10.1515/hf-2019-0005>
2. J. Žigon, Ü. Ayata, R. Zaplotnik, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **The influence of artificial weathering and treatment with FE–DBD plasma in atmospheric conditions on wettability of wood surfaces.** Fortschrittsberichte der Materialforschung und Werkstofftechnik / Bulletin of Materials Research and Engineering, 2019, 7. <https://doi.org/10.21268/20190318-13>
1. J. Žigon, M. Petrič, S. Dahle. **Dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) plasma pretreatment of lignocellulosic materials in air at atmospheric pressure for their improved wettability: A literature review.** Holzforschung, 2018, 72(11), 979-991. <https://doi.org/10.1515/hf-2017-0207>

2.3 Results deposited in open access repositories

Research results were put mainly into the repository Zenodo as an accessible and well-developed service. Published datasets and deposits include Open Research Data for publications published since the start of the action, including transcripts of the Lab Notebooks, but also the Data Management Plan and the contents of large events. Construction details are deposited at GitHub^{14,15} as a collaborative repository, with snapshots published through Zenodo to represent distinctive steps during the development. Published results on Zenodo are as follows:

10. Sebastian Dahle, Megi Pilko, Jure Žigon, Rok Zaplotnik, Marko Petrič, & Matjaž Pavlič. (2020). **Raw and analyzed data for manuscript: "An open-source surface barrier discharge plasma pretreatment reduces cracking of outdoor wood coatings" (Version 1.0.0)** [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4133809>
9. Sebastian Dahle, Irena Uranjek, Jure Žigon, & Sergej Medved. (2020). **Influence of Atmospheric Air Plasma Pre-Treatment of Veneers on the Mechanical Properties**

¹⁴ <https://github.com/SebastianDahle/PlasmaSolution>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/SebastianDahle/Plasma-PSU>

- and Stability of Beech Plywood (Version 1.0.1).** Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3927044>
8. Thomas Gimpel, Jure Žigon, Christian F. Otto, Martin Söftje, Davor Kržišnik, Marko Petrič, & Sebastian Dahle. (2020). **Raw and analyzed data for manuscript: "Wood surface ablation and nanostructuring using a femtosecond laser" (Version 1.0.0)** [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4109039>
 7. Jure Žigon, Janez Kovač, Rok Zaplotnik, Jaša Saražin, Milan Šernek, Marko Petrič, & Sebastian Dahle. (2020). **Enhancement of strength of adhesive bond between wood and metal using atmospheric plasma treatment (Version 1.0.0).** *Cellulose*, 27, 6411–6424. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-020-03212-8> deposited on Zenodo for green Open Access via <https://zenodo.org/record/3994051>
 6. Sebastian Dahle, Jure Žigon, Irena Uranjek, & Marko Petrič. (2020). **Raw and analyzed data for manuscript: "Performance of a water-borne stain on beech, spruce, MDF and OSB improved by plasma pre-treatment" (Version 1.0.0)** [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3733832>
 5. Sebastian Dahle, Jure Žigon, & Marko Petrič. (2019). **Data Management Plan for the MSCA project PlasmaSolution (Version 1.1.1).** Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3530162>
 4. Jure Žigon, Marko Petrič, & Sebastian Dahle. (2019). **Raw and analyzed data to manuscript "Artificially aged spruce and beech wood surfaces reactivated using FE-DBD atmospheric plasma" (Version 1.0.1)** [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2645153>
 3. Sebastian Dahle, Georg Avramidis, Rok Zaplotnik, Gregor Primc, Alenka Vesel, & Miran Mozetič. (2019, October). **First Slovene Plasma Day (Version 1.0.0).** Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3483883>
 2. Sebastian Dahle. (2019, August 28). **SebastianDahle/PlasmaSolution: Plasma equipment (Version 1.1.0).** Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2648789>
 1. Mahdavi-pour, Bahram, Zaplotnik, Rok, Panjan, Matjaž, Oberrath, Jens, & Sebastian Dahle. (2019). **Impact of gas flow on dielectric barrier discharge for air purification (Version 1.0.2).** Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2634047>

2.4 Acquired intellectual property rights

A patent application for one project outcome was submitted at first in 2019 through Luxemburg's Office de la propriété intellectuelle (OPI) and then replaced by the following PCT/EP application:

1. S. Dahle, J. Žigon, M. Petrič, J. Kovač, G. da Cortà. **A plasma device and a method for generating a plasma.** PCT/EP2020/076861, submitted 25.9.2020.

Unlike expected in the proposal, the outcomes of later work packages WP 4 and WP 5, however, did not lead to patent-worthy insights during the project period.

2.5 Outreach activities

A variety of outreach activities were carried out during the project period. These are presented in detail below.

2.5.1 Kick-off event

The project start was used as an opportunity for a first public event. Announcements were posted through press releases on the Tromba website, in the STAZnanost newspaper, and on the social media platforms Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, XING. The event included presentations by the collaboration partners, the Jožef Stefan Institute and the Italian company Certottica, as well as by a delegation from the researcher's previous employer, Clausthal University of Technology. In total, 51 participants from three countries were attending the event, including academic colleagues and interested industrial contacts, as well as the press. Afterwards reports on the event and the project were published in the newspapers STAZnanost, Slovenia Times, and Delo, as well as on uni-lj.si, ditles.si, and slowwwenia.com (see 2.6.1).

2.5.2 Symposium on Wood Surface Engineering

A scientific symposium on wood surface engineering in general with particular focus on plasma applications in the field was foreseen to attract field-specific and regional interest in academic communities. Since several events of the research community in the field were organized in Slovenia toward the end of the project, it was decided to attach the symposium to the conference organized by the host. The researcher thus engaged with the organisation of the International Research Group on Wood Protection's annual conference, where the symposium was included as special session. Unfortunately, the conference could not take place as planned due to the COVID pandemic. The conference was replaced by a small online format with a limited number of selected presentations. One of the contributions by the researcher foreseen for the symposium or special session has been presented at the online conference, but the symposium as such was not possible to conduct due to the public health crisis.

2.5.3 Workshop for academia and industry

In order to spread the plasma technology in the field of wood science and technology both, among academic peers and in the corresponding industrial sectors, as well as to promote the particular kind of plasma technology in the region, a workshop was planned during the project. This workshop was organized together with the Slovene Chamber of Commerce and Industry, with the project partner Jožef Stefan Institute, and with the colleagues at the InnoRenew Center of Excellence in Koper. By suggestion of the chamber of commerce, the scope of the workshop was widened and the event took place as the **1st Slovene plasma day** on Monday September 30th, 2019.¹⁶

In the week leading up to the event, the Slovene festival of Science and the European Researchers' Night 2019 (see sections below) were included into the context, thus enhancing the reach of the relating communication activities.

The event was held at the premises of the newly established Plasma Center and the Department of Wood Science and Technology. The Plasma Day was met with great interest from academia and industry, attracting 88 participants out of 10 different countries. After introductory lectures on the topic given by international presenters, the participants had the chance to visit the

¹⁶ <http://www.bf.uni-lj.si/en/wood-technology/department/organisation/plasma-center/first-slovene-plasma-day/>

laboratories and plasma devices at the host, as well as an exhibition of industrial suppliers of plasma technology. Moreover, a networking session was conducted by colleagues from the chamber of commerce.

A recollection of impressions was afterward published in a short video prepared by a team of the chamber of commerce; which is available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4a9kUy-WbG0> Furthermore, the lectures' presentations are openly available through Zenodo.¹⁷ Reports were published through several channels, including in the news section of the journal *Revija les*.

The event was a great success and will be followed up in collaborations established during the day, as well as through similar events in the following years.

2.5.4 Slovene festival of Science

The 25. Slovene festival of Science was a huge coordinated event across Slovenia with strong international participation, which was held from September 24th through 26th, 2019. Takig place only few days before the 1st Slovene Plasma Day, the researcher participated and used the event for communication activities directed to non-specialists and particularly young people. The visiting groups were led through an interactive demonstration of technical plasmas with engaging content for the target audience.

2.5.5 European Researchers' Nights

The European Researchers' Night 2018 fell into the single possible week to conduct the summer school (see section 2.5.10), as constraint by the two national semester plans. After a full year of planning of the event with the researcher coordinating and managing the activities, it was decided to continue holding the summer school, thus preventing the researcher from participating in person. Seeking advice with the national organizers of the night, unfortunately, the researcher was not included for digital or long-distance participation in any form.

At the European Researchers' Night 2019, the researcher has held an afternoon lecture under the headline »What is a plasma – and why is it cool?« with a diverse set of live experiments. The lecture was included in the central organization and advertised through social media, but also through the faculty's career office. Despite a limited number of participants, the feedback was very positive.

The European Researchers' Night 2020 will only take place digitally due to the ongoing COVID pandemic. The researcher was in contact with the organizers and will participate in the online event.

2.5.6 National science days

The researcher did participate in the yearly national science days. However, the organizers did not allow for large individual activities within the framework, having a dense schedule to cover the various labs and research groups. Thus, the researcher provided materials for presentation at these events without the chance of extended individual interactions.

¹⁷ <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3483884>

2.5.7 Open lab day

The project progress and developments were presented to the public in an Open Lab event on June 4th, 2019. This was shortly after the establishment of the Plasma Center by the Biotechnical faculty, and at a time, when a diverse set of devices and pieces of plasma equipment were made available. The event was advertised through various social media channels as well as through the colleagues' personal networks. In total, 23 participants attended the event with an introductory lecture and practical demonstrations of the various possible applications offered through this technology.

2.5.8 Ambient fairs

The host department participates in the annual Ambient fair, an exhibition and trade show on furniture and interior design with a 30 years history in Ljubljana.¹⁸ The researcher participated in the years 2018 and 2019 with the team organizing the exhibition of the department. In the first year, only a poster was prepared and presented, as no project items had been available for presentation, yet. In 2019, an exhibit was prepared to display a live plasma alongside the poster contribution. For the 2020 fair, a CNC-controlled plasma jet was prepared in such a way, that it can be operated by fair visitors, if appropriate supervision is ensured. Whether the fair will take place, however, is still uncertain due to the ongoing COVID pandemic.

2.5.9 PKP project

The utilization of plasma in the field of wood science and technology has been studied for many decades, but despite many very positive outcomes, the technology has yet to be taken up by industrial stakeholders. In order to clear up the nature of the obstacles preventing a meaningful industrial uptake, so far, and to identify possible pathways to an enhance industrial exploitation, funding for a student project was acquired through the *Po kreativni poti do znanja* (PKP, on the creative path to knowledge) programme.¹⁹ B.Sc. and M.Sc. students from the Biotechnical faculty and the Economical faculty were participating in the project, which was managed at the Economical faculty. The students were introduced to the plasma technology through the researcher as well as at a local distributor of plasma equipment, before they conducted interviews with selected companies from the application sector in mixed pairs, thus ensuring that competences from wood science and economics are present. Based on their interviews, the students identified several obstacles and developed business models that can help surpass these barriers. The PKP project's report will be published online after acceptance by the funder; whereas a short summary is available already in the form of a YouTube video.²⁰

2.5.10 Bilateral summer school

The Marie Curie project was considered an opportunity not only for researcher and host, but also for establishing a more sustained collaboration between the researcher's previous affiliation, Clausthal University of Technology, and the host of the project, University of Ljubljana. Although relations between both universities exist for decades, the collaboration had been minimal for many years, and had not included the hosting department of this action before. In an effort to extend and sustain this, a bilateral course for Master students was organized and included as elective course into the respective study programs. That way, students are presented with an opportunity for international networking, intercultural experiences, and practical

¹⁸ <https://www.furniture-fair.si/>

¹⁹ <https://www.srips-rs.si/razvoj-kadrov/po-kreativni-poti-do-znanja-pkp>

²⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fCdzE5Cwu8>

interdisciplinary work, as the participating study programs include Physics, Chemistry, Materials Science, and Wood Science and Technology.

The interdisciplinary and intercultural effects were particularly fostered through a focus on laboratory work in small focus groups that were composed from participants mixing different professions and nationalities. Interactions, exchange, and innovative thinking were further fostered during a one-week visit through framing of the practical work as “challenge”, defining a broadly defined goal to produce a physical item as solution at which the groups shall compete. The theoretical backgrounds from the different fields required for meaningful solutions were taught through impulse lectures. In the 2018, these were conducted alternating with phases of lab work. In order to enhance the process in 2019, the lectures were held digitally before the exchange, thereby being able to use the one-week stay at the other university for a more focused practical work. The project results were presented by the groups at the end of the exchange in a setting resembling a conference or symposium, where a committee voted the best solution. The group with the best solution was honoured through an award.

The summer school was evaluated very successful and worthwhile by both, the students and the participating university staff. The summer schools were covered on the universities’ news streams as well as in a local newspaper. In addition to that, the summer school provided an opportunity for scientific exchange between the participating staff, scientists, and lecturers from both universities, which already led to small collaborations in the follow-up.

2.5.11 SKOZ project

The interaction with pupils was implemented in a different way than planned in the proposal. Visits in local schools were conducted by colleagues at the department, but to a large degree, this is problematic as foreigner due to the language barrier, since the visits are carried out at levels, where competent English language skills cannot yet be expected. Thus, the visits are carried out in Slovene, only, and hence by the Slovene colleagues. Although the colleagues do now include plasma applications in their presentations, this is no direct activity of the project.

Instead of school visits, a school project with selected pupils was implemented through the *Središče Karijerne Orientacije Zahod* (SKOZ, Career Orientation Center West) programme, which is organized by a neighboring secondary school.²¹ In the project work supervised by the researcher, three pupils developed a hand-held plasma prototype for mobile applications. Thereby, they learned prototyping skills (rapid prototyping and design of a minimum viable product using available resources and tools), practical skills in building the mechanical (housing, air ducts) and electronical (Arduino programming, utilization of ATX power supply) parts of the device, whereas the high-voltage part was covered by the researcher. Moreover, the students included a safety concept similar to commercial plasma products.

Although the initial time plan of the SKOZ project was not met due to several administrative complications, the students have finished a first working prototype after one year of project work, and are planning now to participate with this prototype in several international competitions. Thus, they are advertising for science and they are disseminating the plasma technology in general, as well as the host and this project in particular.

²¹ <https://www.gimvic.org/dejavnosti/skoz/>

2.6 Other dissemination & communication activities

2.6.1 Newspapers & press releases

During the project term, the following newspaper articles and press releases were published:

16. Kooperation mit Ljubljana vertieft. *Report on second bilateral summer school*. 25.09.2019. Web article. Clausthal University of Technology. <https://www.tu-clausthal.de/universitaet/einrichtungen/presse-und-oeffentlichkeitsarbeit/pressemitteilungen/artikel/kooperation-mit-ljubljana-vertieft>
15. Prispevek o projektu PlasmaSolution. *Short summary on PlasmaSolution project*. 03.01.2019. Radio transmission. RTV Slovenija, Radio SI. <https://4d.rtv slo.si/arhiv/euranet-plus/174577924>
14. Za študente magistrskega študija lesarstva smo uspešno izvedli poletno šolo na Tehniški univerzi Clausthal v Nemčiji. *Report on bilateral summer school*. 05.11.2018. Web article. University of Ljubljana. http://www.bf.uni-lj.si/dekanat/novica/?tx_ttnews%5Byear%5D=2018&tx_ttnews%5Bmonth%5D=10&tx_ttnews%5Btt_news%5D=2841&cHash=4af0008ca5e9609f2bfc7053e645118a
13. Ljubljana mu je zlezla pod kožo. *Interview for first MSCA fellowship at University of Ljubljana*. 17.10.2018. Newspaper article. Nedeljski dnevnik.
12. Das beste Regal-Konzept gewinnt. *Report on bilateral summer school*. 06.10.2018. Newspaper article. Goslarsche Zeitung.
11. Summer School: Studierende aus Ljubljana in Clausthal zu Gast. *Report on bilateral summer school*. 04.10.2018. News site of Clausthal University of Technology. <https://www.tu-clausthal.de/presse/nachrichten/details/2443/>
10. Začetek evropskega projekta Marie Sklodowska Curie PlasmaSolution na Univerzi v Ljubljani. *Report on public kick-off event*. 16.09.2018. Web article. https://www.uni-lj.si/v_ospredju/2018083016341935/
9. Na Biotehniški fakulteti v inovativen projekt s področja lesnih premazov. *Article about project contents*. 16.09.2018. Newspaper article. Delo in Dom. <https://deloindom.delo.si/gradnja-in-obnova/na-biotehniski-fakulteti-v-inovativen-projekt-s-podrocja-lesnih-premazov>
8. Biotechnical Faculty with innovative wood coating project. 16.09.2018. Newspaper article. Slovenia Times. <http://www.sloveniatimes.com/biotechnical-faculty-with-innovative-wood-coating-project>
7. Začetek evropskega projekta Marie Sklodowska Curie PlasmaSolution na Univerzi v Ljubljani. *Announcement of project start and kick-off event*. 11.09.2018. Slowwwenia.com http://www.slowwwenia.com/novica/zacetek_evropskega_projekta_marie_sklodowska_curie_plasmasolution_na_univerzi_v_ljubljani.15071871.html
6. PlasmaSolution: Kick-off event. 11.09.2018. Web article. Ditles – Društvo lesarjev Slovenije. <http://www.ditles.si/dogodki/napovednik/plasmasolution-kick-off-event/>

5. EU Marie Skłodowska Curie Project PlasmaSolution launched at University of Ljubljana. 11.09.2018. Web article. University of Ljubljana. <https://www.uni-lj.si/news/news/2018083016414902/>
4. Na Biotehniški fakulteti v inovativen projekt s področja lesnih premazov. *Article about project begin.* 10.09.2018. Newspaper article. STAznanst. <http://znanost.sta.si/2549279/na-biotehniski-fakulteti-v-inovativen-projekt-s-podrocja-lesnih-premazov>
3. Inovativni premazi z biotehniške fakultete. *Announcement of project start and report on kick-off even.* 06.09.2018. Newspaper article. Delo.
2. Predstavitev projekta PlasmaSolution. *Announcement of kick-off event.* 03.09.2018. Web and email announcements. STAznanst. www.sta.si
1. Začetek evropskega projekta Marie Skłodowska Curie PlasmaSolution na Univerzi v Ljubljani. *Announcement of project start and kick-off event.* 03.09.2018. Web article. <http://www.tromba.si/zacetek-evropskega-projekta-marie-sklodowska-curie-plasmasolution-na-univerzi-v-ljubljani/>

2.6.2 Newsletters of professional associations and the Slovenian Chamber of Commerce

The Slovenian Woodworkers' Association covered the project on its website from the beginning (see above), whereas the Slovenian Chamber of Commerce advertised the events organized by the project. Further, the dissemination of the created intellectual property rights and the PKP project (see section 2.5.8) included the corresponding professional associations within the field of work.

2.6.3 YouTube videos

During the first year of the project, a video was produced in collaboration with the Academy of Fine Arts and Design (ALUO), University of Ljubljana. The introductory video was produced both in Slovene and English under the titles “*What is a plasma?*” and “*Kaj je plazma?*”, and it generated 205 and 111 views, respectively, on YouTube until the end of the project. This video production was initially foreseen as diploma project of the student, who produced it, but was finally not used as this by decision of the student. Furthermore, the student was encouraged and supported to engage in video competitions for science communication, but declined to participate.

The collaboration with ALUO was intended to feature a mini series of short videos to cover basic plasma phenomena, applications of the technology used in the project, and the devices constructed and built in the project. Particularly the general contents on plasmas were covered in YouTube videos before, but not consistently within a single channel or series, and especially not in Slovene. For this continued collaboration, a micro media grant was obtained from the Marie Curie Alumni Association. Unfortunately, the student volunteers participating in this second part did leave a few months into the production and the restart of the video production in early 2020 was prevented by the COVID pandemic.

In early 2020, the researcher produced the first two videos to the mini series by himself, these received 141 and 52 views on YouTube until the end of the project. The production of short videos is foreseen to continue in 2021, to further communicate the project's background and the developed technology to non-specialists.

Moreover, the ongoing pandemic and its impact on conferences and events was taken as a chance to publish some of these activities on YouTube, as well, generating e.g. 75 views for the final report to the PKP project (see section 2.5.8).

2.6.4 Project website

The communication of project contents was initially intended via a dedicated website, supposedly prepared with the support of the Academy of Fine Arts and Design. However, the majority of the network within the field is fairly active on Facebook, which allows for creating professional pages that are available also for users not registered on the platform. Given the better reach, reduced efforts, and reduced costs, it was decided to instigate the project website on Facebook via <https://www.facebook.com/PlasmaSolutionMSCA> and thus advertise the project and its results. Posts reached from 41 to over 1400 organic views as well as up to 184 clicks and 55 reactions and comments on individual posts.

2.6.5 Social media and online communication

Before the start of the project, a digital communication strategy was set up, particularly outlining how the target audiences of the project are represented and will be engaged with on different available platforms. The initial selection of platforms included Facebook and Twitter for general public audiences, LinkedIn and Xing for professional audiences, and ResearchGate for academic scholars. In addition to that, OrcID, ResearcherID, Scopus, Publons, and Academia.edu were kept updated as databases to find and access scientific content. Further, a personal website was foreseen as central element, and a Google+ site was supposed to enhance findability of the project content.

In 2018, a focus was given to increase the reach on those platforms and to extent the correlated network through these channels, starting before the official begin of the project. As basic indicators, followers were tracked and the numbers recorded, to allow for later refinement of the strategy and activities. Later, the tracked indicators were extended to monitor interactions (profile views, video views, search views) on the most prominent platform.

At the beginning of 2019, a focused meeting was used to refine the Social Media strategy, to identify the most worthwhile channels, and to define ambitious goals for the remaining project period. Figure 17 shows the development of follower numbers on different social media platforms for the duration of the project (left) as well as an average daily change of follower numbers (right). From both diagrams, it is obvious that the three most successful platforms in declining order are LinkedIn, Facebook, and Xing.

The updated Social Media strategy narrowed down the number channels to be regularly covered to be manageable during a research project. From the three most successful platforms, Facebook was identified as holding the most widespread network in the field of work and having most active contacts, whereas LinkedIn did hold a wider professional audience, that should be engaged with only occasionally. As a German-only platform, Xing was decided not to focus on with much attention, as was decided for other social media. Halfway into the project, the Google+ platform was shut down. The scientific databases were decided to be kept as an online representation of the scientific track record, without much social interactions to be covered.

Figure 17: Development of follower numbers on different Social Media platforms (left), as well as the average follower change per day during the project period (right).

Based on the assessment in January 2019, goals were designed for the continued social media coverage, for each platform, a minimal and a more ambitious goal were defined. As shown in Table 1, the two platforms identified as most important communication channels well met the defined goals. With the occurrence of delays from risks and the pandemic appearing in 2020, the activities on social media had to be strongly reduced and consequently, the ambitious goals were not nearly met. Moreover, this led to the less important social media platforms falling short of even the minimal goals defined in January 2019. However, a significant increase on all platforms is obvious, rendering this a successful project activity nonetheless.

Table 1: Follower on social media channels before, during and after the project, as well as the minimal and ambitious goals set out after the first quarter of the project period.

Platform	Before project	Status on 1.1.2019	Minimal goals	Ambitious goals	After project
LinkedIn	50	298	500	700	537
Facebook	100	289	400	500	418
XING	50	233	300	350	289
ResearchGate	80	132	200	350	164
Twitter	0	19	100	200	67

2.7 Other exploitation and dissemination

2.7.1 Plasma Center at Biotechnical faculty

The developments, technology, and collaborations brought about through this project was acknowledged by the University of Ljubljana to establish a Plasma Center at the Biotechnical Faculty on May 27th, 2019.²² The activities are coordinated by the head of the center, currently represented by the researcher of this project, as well as the steering board of four professors at the faculty. The main areas of the Plasma Center's operations are further development of plasma

²² <http://www.bf.uni-lj.si/en/wood-technology/department/organisation/plasma-center/>

technology, the development of new applications, and the implementation of joint research and development projects with industry partners and academic circles.

The topics include, among others:

- Surface treatments of surfaces of various materials and composites for further processing, such as coating, bonding or producing composites,
- Deposition of coatings on various surfaces,
- Removal of contaminants and impurities from surfaces,
- Purification of gases, i.e. removal of pollutants and inactivation of allergens and pathogens,
- Processing of value-added gases in chemical and process engineering,
- Wastewater treatment,
- And many more.

Thereby, the center provides a common basis for all activities in the field of plasma applications at the Biotechnical Faculty, including:

- Establishment of collaboration between researchers, academic teachers and technical staff within Biotechnical faculty, as well as at other faculties of the University of Ljubljana and from other institutions,
- Support at preparation of project proposals, so on the national and European level, as well as globally,
- Support at various plasma applications by offering the infrastructure.

2.7.2 Proposal submitted for ERA Chair

In November 2019, the researcher submitted a proposal under the title OpenPlasma ERA Chair to the WIDESPREAD-06-2020 topic of the H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020-6 call. In preparation of the proposal, the researcher acquired and coordinated 50 partner organizations including universities, research institutes, companies, public bodies, and other supporting organizations from Slovenia, Europe and world-wide. Moreover, 12 out of 26 faculties and academies at University of Ljubljana had agreed their collaboration in the project. Although the proposal was not successful, the process of coordinating such a large consortium for a single proposal was a huge learning experience for the researcher and presented a unique opportunity to expand the personal network. Some of the contacts have been followed up after the receiving the rejection, thus trying to implement individual ideas on a smaller scale than foreseen with the ERA Chair.

2.7.3 Proposal submitted to ARRS

Based on preliminary results from the project and a newly initiated collaboration with the Institute for Cellulose and Paper, a proposal for a national research project was submitted in response to the yearly call for individual research projects. The proposal under the title “SmartWood - Surface functionalization of wood for smart applications” was intended to combine plasma, printing, and organic electronics on wooden work pieces with the aim to functionalize wood and wood composites for smart applications. These smart application would have involved conductive inks and coatings for sensing applications, monitoring of moisture or structural stiffness through conductive lines and sensing structures to help prevent degradation of wood structures due to deterioration, as well as new applications based in wood production (smart furniture and smart wood structures). Further printed electronics components would have involved transistors, conductors, resistors, displays, sensors, buttons and actuators,

batteries and antennas. During the later project phases, the usability of wood-printed circuits would have been tested for solder-on electronics and for the use with different printed electronic sensors, components, and modules, including an all-printed RFID tag. Unfortunately, the project fall short in relation to the available national budget and did not receive funding.

2.7.4 Participation in proposal to Biobased industries – joint undertaking

Based on the expertise and the developments of this projects, the researcher was invited to participate in a consortial proposal to a recent call under the bio-based industries joint undertaking. The proposal including and extending on outcomes from this report was submitted under the title ByeOpack was submitted on September 3rd to the BBI-2020-SO3-D4 topic of the H2020-BBI-JTI-2020 call.

2.7.5 Open Science activities

The researcher participated across Slovenia at events advocating for Open Science, held presentations at workshops in Maribor and Ljubljana (see section 2.1), and collaborated at further workshops. During the project period, the researcher became member of the Research Data Alliance's Slovenian node and engaged with Eurodoc's Open Science Working Group.

As per voluntary opt-in to the Open Research Data pilot, the researcher provided open access to the research data produced during the project. The data was made available in correlation with publications, including scientific articles, conference contributions, and other output. That way, the published data is well-structured, has a defined scope, and an increased findability and reusability are achieved through the combined publication of manuscripts and data. The majority of datasets was published through Zenodo, other datasets are deposited on the hosts repository²³, GitHub,^{24,25} and GrabCAD²⁶. Further details are discussed with the data management plan.^{27,28}

The approach to Open Methodology as described in the proposal was extended during the project period, such that the entire developments are being made openly available. In particular, this aims at Open Laboratory Equipment as strongly overlooked branch of Open Science. Unfortunately, a hands-on workshop that was envisioned to and planned together with the Young Academy of Slovenia for summer 2020 was not possible to implement due to the COVID pandemic, but will prospectively be held in 2021. Thus, attention and interest into this area shall be attracted with benefits for many research fields and for society in general. In the meantime, the equipment and methodologies developed during this project are being made available through combinations of communication and dissemination activities. These include scientific Open Access publications, openly published snapshots of construction details (Zenodo), construction files being made available on collaborative development platforms (GitHub, GrabCAD), engaging YouTube videos with overview and background information, Open Lab Days, as well as announcements and dissemination on Social Media channels.

²³ <https://repozitorij.uni-lj.si/info/index.php/slo/>

²⁴ <https://github.com/SebastianDahle/PlasmaSolution>

²⁵ <https://github.com/SebastianDahle/Plasma-PSU>

²⁶ <https://workbench.grabcad.com/sebastian.dahle-1>

²⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3530162>

²⁸ <https://argos.openaire.eu/explore-plans/publicOverview/1314b654-4e93-46b3-bc97-7d075ab5376e>

The usage of Open Lab Notebooks as described by Foster Open Science²⁹ and the Open Lab Notebook³⁰ was not implemented to full extent. On one hand, the utilization of an online-only lab notebook showed impractical while working with chemicals. On the other hand, the tested digital systems were less intuitive to utilize and did not reduce time efforts after several lab days. Therefore, a simplified system was implemented for this project, which combined conventional lab notebooks with digitalization after completion of the lab work, online spreadsheets on a cloud service, and direct data deposition into the cloud folder structure, wherever possible. The complete lab notes for experiments were published together with the raw and analysed data upon publication of any results. However, no pre-registration of research³¹ was carried out during this project.

2.7.6 Integration in national projects

The equipment developed in the project and the researcher's expertise has been included in two nationally funded research actions, the national project "Performance of wood and lignocellulosic composites in outdoor applications" and the national research programme "Wood and lignocellulosic composites". In doing so, additional outcomes for these projects were generated, that have been published as indicated in sections 2.1, 2.2, and 2.3.

3 Update of the data management plan

The initial data management plan included utilization of the departments shared data infrastructure, a network area storage (NAS) service outsourced by the faculty. The downside to this service is the limited accessibility: Access from outside the department, including outside a VPN connection, is not possible, thus preventing shared access with project partners or supporting colleagues in other departments of the university; even not all computers at the department are granted access to the shared disk. A better collaborative work on individual parts of the work packages is enabled through the usage of other outside cloud services, which is allowed under the hosts policies. Measurement raw data and all office materials were thus moved to the researcher's private Google drive under shared access with the collaborating colleagues as required. Construction data was moved to GitHub, where the reuse by and the collaboration with external parties is openly rendered possible. Mechanical constructions were additionally uploaded to a GrabCAD workbench, thus allowing collaborators to view original, proprietary files through the website's service, and an easier collaboration was established. Moreover, construction files partially are released openly through GrabCAD³², the remaining files will be released within 6 months after the end of the project, to enable additional reuse and enhance the findability. Finally, additional file formats were included in the data management plan, as requirements for additional software and lab devices became apparent.

The first versions of the data management plan were drafted in the DMPonline tool³³, where public view is enabled. The initial data management plan is additionally published openly on Zenodo.³⁴ As the European Commissions ARGOS platform became available, the updated versions were moved over to this new service, where the updated version of the DMP was openly published.³⁵ A final data management plan containing the most recent updates will be

²⁹ <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/taxonomy/term/104>

³⁰ <https://openlabnotebooks.org/>

³¹ <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/prereg>

³² <https://workbench.grabcad.com/sebastian.dahle-1>

³³ <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/plans/18705/export.pdf>

³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3530162>

³⁵ <https://argos.openaire.eu/explore-plans/publicOverview/1314b654-4e93-46b3-bc97-7d075ab5376e>

released again as an update through Argos and Zenodo within a half year following the end of the action.

4 Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous reviews

Not applicable.

5 Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2 (if applicable)

Deviations from the description of the action had to be taken in work package 1 and work package 4. The combined impacts of the encountered difficulties as well as the restricted laboratory access during the COVID pandemic prevented the successful completion of work packages 4 and 5.

5.1 Tasks

As indicated by the evaluators in the summary report, the time to build and set up equipment completely anew is problematic to the project duration. Therefore, electronics and construction details were to be transferred from earlier projects. However, problems arose with those parts and the previously ensured support by the corresponding start-up company was not sufficiently met. Consequently in work package 1, risk 1 was encountered and the suggested mitigation measure was taken, adapting the construction due to the unforeseen disturbance. In particular, significant efforts were required to test several concepts of high voltage power supplies and to sufficiently implement a working solution.

In work package 3, the investigations of wetting behaviours yielded previously unknown effects and an additional level of complexity that was not previously reported. Consequently, risk 4 did apply, preventing the deduction of a generalized model. However, the encountered effects and insights did lead to additional publications that are under review at the time of submission of this report. It is expected, that the new insights will motivate additional projects in the future to investigate the nature of the observed effects and clear up the physicochemical processes.

In work package 4, problems with film adhesion on the substrate were foreseen (risk 5). However, in a transfer from the plasma setup utilized in the preliminary experiments towards a way of implementation suited for a later transfer into industrial practice, no film formation through plasma-induced curing could be achieved. As mitigation measure, the type of plasma setup was changed and additional equipment was developed and implemented. With limited access to the laboratory during the second project year due to the COVID pandemic, however, still no sufficient film formation through plasma curing was achieved until the end of the project period. This further impaired work package 5, rendering it impossible to fulfil the work planned for complex formulations.

In conclusion, the objective (ii) was only partially met and objective (iii) was not possible to cover, thus not meeting the ambitious goal of the project.

5.2 Use of resources

Not applicable.